

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Information Managers as Change Agents in achieving Sustainable Development in the 21st Century

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to examine the role of information managers and libraries in accomplishing Nigeria's sustainable development goals in the 21st Century. The paper explored the notion of sustainable development, examines the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) including their respective targets. It identifies and discusses the role of libraries and information managers (librarians) in achieving SDGs, as well as the philosophy of information theory of communication as proposed by Claude Shannon (1948). Libraries all over the world offer a variety of products and services that support the accomplishment of all 17 SDGs. Libraries are secure, friendly spaces at the heart of communities, fostering reading and providing free access to information. Libraries are vital instruments in society, and they play a critical role in accomplishing long-term development goals. Citizens must be well informed if Nigeria's sustainable development goals are to be met and sustained. This can be accomplished by selecting, processing, organizing, and disseminating information based on the parameter of development as indicated in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and organizing training programs or forums where issues such education, environmental, climate change, gender inequality and health issues can be discussed, and so on.

Keywords: Information manager; librarian; library; information sustainable development Goals

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Introduction

Sustainability is a popular topic in most political and academic discuss but there is a dearth of it within the discipline of Library & Information Science. The concept enunciates a strong normative value towards equitable resource utilization in attaining intergenerational justice. This philosophy, entrenches the principles of conservation of natural environment as well as global equity. The world is changing and many scholars have had to grapples with the complications_brought about by a fast-changing world where by the living pattern of the present generation consciously altered to a more beneficial way, to accommodate generations yet unborn (Lewis, Kenerson, Sorrentino & Rowse, 2019). The role of Information Managers also known as Librarians in this transition is essential, as Information Managers play a

critical role in accomplishing long-term development goals through the provision of essential information services which has the capacity to enhance the quality of decision taken by individual members of the society towards in achieving the set goals.

Expectantly, the drive of this new orientation of sustainability is being spearheaded by the United Nations through a framework known as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The SDGs are global in nature, taking into cognizance national realities, capacities and level of development. In Nigeria, like other nations, the expectation is that all hands must be on deck in attaining these goals. However, it appears from available records, that countries from third world nations especially from the Africa sub-region are lagging behind in the attainment of these global agenda. (Onyam & Benson, 2020).